

A Study Of Teachers' Code Of Conduct At Secondary School Level In Perspective Of Teaching Of Islamic Studies And Basic Islamic Information

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Islamic Studies, Code of conduct, Teachers' perceptions, Teachers' Practices, Secondary School Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5799664</p>	<p><i>Teachers' code of conduct prescribed by the government of Punjab Pakistan along with other contents consists of teachers responsibilities regarding teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. This code abides educational management and monitoring authorities about the implementation of this code. The present study explores secondary school teachers' role in teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. The survey method using four questionnaires were used as tools of data collection. One hundred secondary school heads and one hundred secondary school teachers whereas one thousand students of the same schools from four districts of the Punjab Pakistan was sample of the study that was chosen through multistage sampling. One-way ANOVA test along with LSD test was used to analyse the collected data. The results revealed that the majority of teachers had good understanding about the teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information but they did not act upon it as narrated in teachers' code of conduct. In the light of the findings of the study it is recommended that educational administration and monitoring authorities should use this aspect while recruiting, training and observing their teachers during teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information.</i></p>

Introduction

Many studies concluded that religion has deep impact on the manners and ethics of the person. It is admitted that religion has a positive impact on ethical status and moral development. The religious teachings are everlasting and played as self-motive factor. Like each religion Islam is also comprised of a set of moral values or laws that is much enhanced and complete as compare to other religions. The sole source of moral laws is divine teachings of God and that laws have some specific characters like they are unconditional, endless and consistent. Education in other word is a key source of moral training in the world. Moral laws or principals are specific with regard of their uniqueness. These laws are not for specific time but these are everlasting time or situation never altar these laws. Morals are important as they play an element of standardize the behavior of the professionals and they are source of continuity and survival of the profession (Deshach, 2014). Morals are important for general life as they have strong impact on behavior of a person. Morals are a source of professionalism as they provide basis for the profession. A person equipped with professional morals performed better in the profession. Teaching profession also armed with some key professional morals. Capli (2015) describes that the teacher has a vital role in moral development of the students and is an effective link between the school and the community. Teacher also cooperates with the parents in levitation the students in promoting morals. Teachers' own morals and scientific capabilities reflected through their practices play a vital role in developing a new generation. Teaching profession demands more moral training as teachers are considered moral agents that transferred morals to the younger generation.

In common a morally trained person reflected more civilized that is better for the society. Nadia (2015) revealed the significance of professional ethics or morals for teachers in educational institutions and recognized that it helps teachers in increasing people's knowledge of ethics and values through learning the good and bad. Moral values provide basic principles that helped to differentiate good and bad deeds. It is important for the moral training of the coming generation. In present most of the teachers training programs have contents regarding teachers' code of conduct including moral training. Capli (2015) found that many countries have started to draft codes of ethics for the teaching profession for the cause of attaining the anticipated objectives formulated for the teaching profession.

Teachers' code of conduct especially about moral training or education is vital document that helps in producing trained teachers that able to produce morally trained students to improve the moral status of the society. Al-Rawahy (2013) found that being well-informed is crucial for success of a person and society gaining

knowledge is among major Islamic impacts toward the betterment of mankind. Teachers are main agents that played important role in transferring the knowledge to the new generation.

Quran is a basic source of ethics for the Muslim that provide a complete way of life for them (Al-A'ali, 2008). Holy Quran is fundamental source of all kind of knowledge that is granted by Allah almighty. The very first part of the Quran was about reading its mean acquiring knowledge is basic obligation for all the Muslims. That indicates in religion of Islam teaching and learning is not just optional activity but it is binding task for every follower. No doubt Islam is only one religion that is very strict about learning. There is famous saying (Hadees-E-Pak) of Hazrat Muhammad (SAW) that He (SAW) was sent by Allah as teacher (Muallam). In teaching process teachers played central role that enhance the tasks of the teachers. In religion Islam teaching is considered as holy profession where teachers enjoyed uphold status. That status of teachers abides some special duties and responsibilities with regard of their own level of knowledge and professional qualities.

In the Islamic system teachers have a unique status with regard of moral and social betterment. Thereputation of Islamic society could be measured keeping the status of the teachers in view. In Islam teachers are given so high position in the society as they are considered the spiritual fathers of the students thus the teachers are given so highly respected status. In the Islamic society, the teachers enjoy a high social prestige that is visible in the first verse of the Holy Quran that fortified learning and teaching process. The Quran says: "God will exalt those of you who believe and those who are given knowledge to high degrees." (58:11). Teachers adored vital role because they ranked the status of the heirs of the Prophets. That indicates the importance of teachers and all the activities performed by them during the process of teaching. Al-Mafdi (2004) studied that the teacher is the pillar of the educational process that help and guide in preparing the competent manpower to meet the needs of the society and influencing the behavior and morals of the society by training the new generation.

Abdur Razzaq, (2012) codes that Holy Quran says among Muslims the best person is a person who espouses good moral foundations and invites others to practice such actions. The teachers are accountable for not only preserving the cultural practices and transmitting them from generation to generation as this is necessary for making the growth and stability of society.

Teachers performed their role just not teaching the course contents in a proper way they are responsible for preservation of the existing cultural tradition of the society. Teachers' role in Islam is not teaching the course content only teachers are also responsible to teach and educate about difference of good and bad deeds. Thus teachers are not only educators but they are social and ethic trainers also. Yunanda and Majid (2011) have claimed that the religion Islam has divine values that play an important role to implant ethical values. It is admitted fact that divine values and principles of Islam that are connected to general learning and social training are everlasting and present actual solution of the problems ever raise. To present original and real face of Islam teachers have to play key role because without good and well trained teachers it cannot be done. That is why this study focused upon to study the role of teachers in teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information as they are narrated in the teachers' code of conduct.

Literature Review

Allah hopes the Muslims they to do good deeds, they should be responsible and answerable to Allah the Almighty (At-Tawbah, 9, p. 105) and the Muslims always should be ready to perform good deeds (Al-Baqarah, 2, p. 148; Al-Anbiya, 21, p. 73). Education meaning for Muslims is a religious obligation that continued through all the times and the complete life of a Muslim. Education is considered set of activities like worship, good deeds, beliefs and spirits.

Islam is a complete code of life that provides entire gaudiness about ethics, believes, actions, worship and all matters of daily life. Ethics are a combination of principles that differentiate right, acceptable deeds from bad or wrong. Islamic ethics based upon the ethical system that formed by the teachings of the Quran and through actions and words of the Holy prophet Muhammad (P.B.U.H). The Islamic ethics centered upon the Quran and Sunnah (Abdurezak, 2011). Holy Quran and Sunnah are two main and undoubted source of Islamic education. The ethics works as a compass that lead the people how should they behave with each other and lived their lives in the society (Sadia, 2015). Ibn Miskawayh in his book *Tahdhib Al-Akhlaq* narrated that teacher acts as trainer who left an impact on the younger generation, teachers moral and behavior taken as role model not for the students even within the entire Muslim community (Nadia, 2015). In whole Muslim world teachers are always considered most respected persons. Even they are taken the spiritual fathers of the students and successors of the holy prophet Muhammad (P.B.U.H). In the Muslim societies teachers ever highly respected one who disobey the teachers is considered doom. Muslim teachers ever considered responsible for teaching and training of their students especially respect of teachers and all that who are elders or seniors even the young. Students should be trained how to respect others is considered an important responsibility for Muslim teachers (Mohd, 2013). Respect of teachers is always remain a key point of each educational system but in Islam respect of teachers is binding upon pupils as a religious obligation. Islam basically is religion of obedience. Obedience to God and obedience to prophet Muhammad (P.H.U.B) is bidding obligation for each follower.

Many Previous studies about teachers' role in giving of Islamic Education have found that the basics of teaching practice are the participation of students, feedback to the students, teaching resources and procedure of implementation of content activities (Ghani, Khadijah, & Embi, 2003). Teachers and students' active participation as in general education is important. Teachers way of practicing or pedagogy play important role in transferring of knowledge. Van Driel and Berry (2012) stressed that when the teachers have effective pedagogical skill and content, it make them able to realize how students learn but when teachers not able to learn they should enhance the level of professionalism of a teacher. Teachers' skill of pedagogy and ability to guess the needs and abilities of the students make learning process result oriented. Adnan (2002) found that the teaching of religious studies is very important in Islam religion. Muslims engagement in worship is a source of developing good character because worship is a long term process that transforms them into upright and morally trained individuals. Islamic education and its teaching wish to create sense of thinking and awareness about the creation of the universe and beginning and existence of life (An-Nahlawi, 2010). All divine religions of the world based on truth and invite their followers to explore the nature discover the reality. Islam as religion imposes binding upon its followers that they think about the creation of the universe for the cause of revealed the truth. Thus one of the main objectives of education in Islam is provoking sense of thinking in its followers.

The Islamic teachings are very close to that of science as Islam in words of Holy Quran declared about study of nature and to reach its creator the Allah. Islamic teachings are much closed to nature and science is knowledge of nature itself. Islam motivates its followers upon the investigation of nature that leads toward the reality of factual truth that is hidden in creation of this universe.

Asyafah (2014) found that understanding of religion depends on the method of teaching. Muslim scholar and teachers during teaching used both approaches of teaching individually and in small groups (Al-Sharaf, 2013). In Islam the aim of education is to provide such opportunities to the *students* that they know about themselves. In presently while teaching Islamic religion classes teachers are not using the teaching methods that are recommended by Quran and Sunnah (Hamad, 2004). Holy Quran is not a divine book it is also provides a complete code of life including how to teach. Holy Quran narrated how to teach and it is further explained by Holy prophet Muhammad (PBUH) but during teaching of Quran Muslim teachers are not following that rules. A study reported that Malaysian teachers felt moral values are necessary part of the curriculum that they have to teach but mostly it is not done by them as it is prescribed in the curriculum (Thomas, 2003). One of the meaning of Education is to train persons socially in such manners that they become able to spend balanced life as civilized members of the society. Moral values are part of the curriculum and teachers are confined to train their students. Unfortunately, in many countries of the world mostly concerned authorities are not much focused on moral training of the new generation.

With the passage of time and advancement in teaching methodology the quality teaching pedagogy is considered as an essential component of today teaching (Arifin, 2004). Pedagogy adopted by the teachers is key feature of teaching process. In this period of scientific exploration use of modern tools and technology in teaching process may make it more effective. In teaching of Islamic education to the new generation the use of modern technology may improve quality of teaching and make this process interesting and result oriented.

Statement of the Problem

A number of studies are quoted by various researchers about the serious concern that Pakistan is far behind from the other nations of the world in the field of education itself and also in many other fields of life as education undoubtedly affects other spheres of life. There is no second opinion that educated people surely play their role better in the development of the country. Present study on the title "A study of teachers' code of conduct at secondary school level in perspective of teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information" was conducted to explore the teachers' perceptions, teachers' practices and explore the gaps between teachers' perceptions and practices in views of their head teachers and students opinions. Pakistan is an Islamic country and majority of teachers are Muslims thus the study was focused on the teachings of Islam in the shape of teaching of Islamic studies. The study was to gage the responsibilities of the teachers that they perform in educating the students and making the nation educated.

The Researchers were interested to study teachers' perceptions and practices about the key factors teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. To explore the gaps between teachers' perceptions and practices regarding teaching of Islamic studies and provision of basic Islamic information was main aim of the study. Financial and time resources always have influencing role on completion of the study due to these restrains the present study was narrowed to the secondary schools working in public sector in some selected districts of province Punjab of Pakistan only.

Research Questions

The present study dedicated to explore the answers to the following research questions

1. To what degree teachers are aware about code of conduct regarding teaching of Islamic studies and students religious training?
2. To what degree teachers are practicing about code of conduct in respect of teaching of Islamic studies and students religious training?

3. To what extent there are gaps between teachers 'perceptions and practices relating of teaching of Islamic studies and students religious training as given in teachers' code of conduct?

Significance of the Study

The present study has discovered the knowledge and practices of teachers about the teachers' code of conduct for school teachers in respect of teaching of Islamic studies and students religious training. The conclusions or findings of the study may prove fruitful for the concerned authorities in understanding the gaps between requisite and actual situations in schools. Supervisory and managerial officers can make strategies for the improvement regarding practices of the teachers. The study can be helpful for the monitoring officers to solve the issues about decline of teachers' practices with regard of teaching of Islamic studies and students' religious training as prescribed in teachers' code of conduct. The study will clearly assist our educational executives and educational managers in achieving national educational objectives. Our home land's full name is Islamic Republic Pakistan thus the results of the study will be helpful for concerned authorities in improving teaching of Islamic studies and students' religious training. The study will positively motivate our teachers about implementation of teachers' code of conduct.

Research Methodology

The study was related to present situation thus descriptive research method was used. Four different type questionnaires were used as data collection tools. The survey method was adopted for data collection. In survey method vast location and large number of population may become a factor of probable obstacles that influence on completion of the study well on time. Thus study was delimited to secondary schools of four districts of Punjab province of Pakistan.

Population

Population of the study was comprised of all the government secondary school teachers working in public institutions in the Punjab province of Pakistan.

Sample

Multistage cluster sampling technique was used while sampling of the study. The Punjab province is comprised of nine divisions and thirty-six districts. Multan and Bahawalpur division were taken as sample divisions. Then two districts from each sample division thus District Bahawalpur, Bahawalnagar, Multan and Vehari were taken as part of the study. From each sample district total twenty five schools were taken as sample of schools. Using multistage sampling the head teacher of the school, one secondary school teacher and ten students from each school were taken as sample of the study.

Research Instruments

Four different type questionnaire (based on same content) on five-point Likert scale were developed. These all four type questionnaires were consisting ten (10) items that were related to Provision of proper help for assembly items, Addressing on different topics for students' moral and character building, Monitoring of students' general physical cleanliness, Inspiring of creative thoughts of students, Memorizing Zuhar prayer with the students, Teaching of Nazara and Urdu translation of Holy Quran, Teaching of memorization of Holy Quran, Teaching of Urdu translation of Suras and Ahdees and Teaching of Arkaan-E-Islam.

All four research instruments were designed on the base of deep study of relevant literature on the conduct of the teachers. The questionnaires were based on same content however the style of asking about information was different. Among the questionnaire first was about teachers' perceptions, second was related to teachers' practices, the third was to know head teachers' observations and the fourth questionnaire was to measure students' opinions regarding teachers' practices.

Content validity and face strength of the questionnaires was evaluated through experts' opinions. A pilot study was also done by using the tools on a sample of 10 secondary schools. Reliability of the questionnaires was examined through Cronbach's alpha value. The value of r (correlation) for four questionnaires was ranged 0.883 to 0.885. It was an indicator toward reliability of the data collecting tools. Item wise detail is given below:

Item No.	TP (r)value	TPR (r)value	HTO (r)value	STO(r)value
1.	0.885	0.882	0.886	0.882
2.	0.887	0.881	0.882	0.886
3.	0.881	0.884	0.887	0.882
4.	0.883	0.886	0.881	0.886
5.	0.886	0.881	0.882	0.886
6.	0.882	0.881	0.883	0.882
7.	0.885	0.884	0.887	0.886
8.	0.884	0.887	0.886	0.887
9.	0.886	0.881	0.882	0.887
10.	0.882	0.886	0.887	0.881
Average	0.884	0.883	0.884	0.885

Data Collection

The data was collected through questionnaires. Total twelve hundreds questionnaires were conveyed and collected personally by the researchers. The return rate of the questionnaires was hundred percent. The researchers distributed the relative four type questionnaires to the concerned participants along with verbal and written guidelines about responding the statements. Due to environmental, cultural, time and financial restrictions and research ethics in view, no electronic or pictorial recording was done during data collection. The participants of the study were informed that their identity and personal information will never be reported to any one at any stage. Such information will be used only for research purposes.

Data Analysis

Data analysis of the collected data was made by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. A combine sheet of SPSS was prepared that was included of all four separate SPSS sheets. The merged SPSS sheet was used to apply One-way ANOVA test along with LSD test. That analysis item wise analysis was made to expose the mean score, F-value and significance value. Differences between various groups of the respondents were explored by applying LSD test. One-way ANOVA test was used to explore the gaps between teachers' perceptions and their practices was explored through one-way ANOVA test.

Results and Interpretation

The data of present study was linked to the ten test items related to teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. The data was concerned with teachers' perceptions and their practices as per their own claim. For the cause of counter verification data regarding the test items was also taken from the head teachers and the students concerned as their observations. As data was collected from four strains to analyze it by using same test one way ANOVA was used. Consequently, data was processed and results concerning to the test items (statements) already mentioned were displayed in same table to easily view and compare teachers' perceptions, teachers' practices, head teachers' observations and students' observation. The criterion of acceptance regarding mean score value was fixed three (3) and above. Mean score ranged 4.00 and above was taken strong agreement, mean score ranged 3.00 to 3.99 was taken weak agreement and mean score value 2.99 and below was taken as respondents' disagreement to the statement. The criterion of acceptance regarding the mean difference was considered significant at the 0.05 level. Under each table brief explanation of the results has been given to simplify its outcomes.

Table 1

Teacher teaches with kindness

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	4.02							
TPR	3.89	45.24	0.000	0.126	0.826*	0.700*	-0.948*	0.822*
HTO	3.07			(0.213)	(0.000)	(0.004)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	3.19							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

The table is about "Teacher teaches with kindness". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 4.02. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.89 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 3.07 while mean score value of students' observations STO is 3.19. These values indicates that teachers have strong thinking about teaching with kindness (mean 4.02). They think that teaching with kindness may be helpful for learning. They also acknowledge and follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.89). The analysis of mean score of head teachers and students signposts that in observation of head teachers (mean 3.07) and in observation of students (mean 3.19), this code is followed by teachers in practice but not in strong position as they claimed in their perceptions and wills.

The ANOVA analysis ($f=45.24$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates insignificant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and teachers' practices (0.126, $p=0.213$), a significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.826, $p=0.000$) and significant mean difference between teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.700, $p=0.004$). The difference between teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-0.948, $p=0.000$) and difference between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is also eminent from the data (-0.822, $p=0.000$).

This discovers a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices. It indicates that teachers admit this code. They will to follow it but do not follow in their practices strongly.

Table 2

Teacher provides proper help for Naat Recitation and other items for assembly events

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	3.96							
TPR	3.94	97.29	0.000	0.019	-1.104*	1.085*	1.207 *	1.189*
HTO	2.75			(0.076)	(0.000)	(0.038)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	2.86							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 2 is about "Teacher provides proper help for Naat recitation and other items for assembly events". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 3.96. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.94, mean score of head teachers' observations is 2.75 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 2.86. These values indicate that teachers have strong positive thinking about provision of proper help for Naat and other items for assembly events (mean 3.96). Whereas, analysis of mean score of head teachers and students regarding their observation about the application of this code by teachers in observation of head teachers (mean 2.75) and in observation of students (2.86), points out that this code is not followed strongly by teachers in practice in accordance to their perceptions, claims and point of view.

ANOVA analysis ($F=97.29$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a strong significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates insignificant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and teachers' practices (0.019, $p=0.076$), and significant difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (-1.104, $p=0.000$), the significant mean difference between teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (-1.085, $p=0.038$). The significant difference between teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-1.207, $p=0.000$), while difference between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (-1.189, $p=0.000$).

This explores a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices; it indicates that teachers do not follow/ poorly follow this code as head teachers' observations (mean 2.75) and that of students (2.86) affirm this.

Table 3

Teacher addresses in assembly for students' moral and character building

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	4.14							
TPR	3.93	22.96	0.000	0.207*	0.296*	0.089	-0.752*	0.544*
HTO	3.39			(0.027)	(0.002)	(0.343)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	3.84							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 3 is about "Teacher addresses in assembly for students' moral and character building". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 4.14. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.93, mean score of head teachers' observations is 3.39 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 3.84. These values indicate that teachers have strong agreement and they think that their addressing in assembly for students' moral and character building helpful to improve learning. They confess that they follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.93). Although, analysis of mean score of head teachers and students indicates that in observation of head teachers (mean 3.39) and in observation of students (3.84), this code is poorly followed by teachers in practice.

The ANOVA analysis ($F=22.96$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and teachers' practices (0.207, $p=0.027$), teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.296, $p=0.002$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-0.752, $p=0.000$) and difference between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation (0.544, $p=0.000$).

This explores a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices; it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices according to their perceptions.

Table 4

Teacher monitors students' general physical appearance i.e. cutting of hair, nails

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	4.00							
TPR	3.73	61.07	0.000	0.270*	0.530*	0.259*	-1.337*	1.067*
HTO	2.66			(0.010)	(0.000)	(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	3.47							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 4 is about "Teacher monitors students' general physical appearance i.e. cutting of hair nails". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 4.00. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.73 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 2.66 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 3.47. These values indicate that teachers have strong thinking. They think that monitoring students' general physical appearance i.e. cutting of hair, nails may be helpful to improve teaching results. They also admit that they follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.73). While, analysis of mean score of head teachers and students regarding their observation is (mean 2.66) and (mean 3.47) respectively, that indicates this code is weakly followed by teachers in practice.

The ANOVA analysis ($F=61.07$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and teachers' practices (0.270, $p=0.010$), and teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.530, $p=0.000$), significant mean difference between teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.259, $p=0.013$). The difference between teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-1.337, $p=0.000$), while difference between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (-1.067, $p=0.000$).

This explores a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices; it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices.

Table 5

Teacher supports creative thoughts/thinking of students

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	4.03							
TPR	4.03	97.35	0.000	0.004	0.807*	0.804*	-1.400*	-1.396 *
HTO	2.63			(0.970)	(0.000)	(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	3.23							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 5 is about "Teacher supports creative thoughts/thinking of students". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 4.03. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 4.03 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 2.63 though mean score value of students' observations is 3.23. These values indicate that teachers have strong perception and they think that supporting creative thoughts/thinking of students can be helpful to improve results. They also admit that they follow this code in their practices (mean score 4.03). Whereas, analysis of mean score of head teachers and students regarding indicates that in observation of head teachers (mean 2.63) and in observation of students (3.23), this code is not followed by teachers in practice.

Results of ANOVA analysis ($f=97.35$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.807, $p=0.000$), teachers' claim about their practice and students' observation (0.804, $p=0.013$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-1.400, $p=0.000$) and teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (-1.396, $p=0.000$).

This proves a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices as head teachers' opinions students' observations do not prove teachers' claim.

Table 6

Teacher offers Zuhar prayer with the students

Variables	Mean	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO

	score	F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	3.62							
TPR	2.76	31.96	0.000	-0.111	0.163	0.274*	0.859*	0.970*
HTO	2.56			(0.306)	(0.035)	(0.012)	(0.000)	(0.000)
STO	3.46							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 6 is about "Teacher offers Zuhar prayer with the students". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 3.62. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 2.76 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 2.56 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 3.46. These values indicate that teachers have poor perception about offering Zuhar prayer with the students (mean 3.62). They also admit that they do not follow this code in their practices (mean score 2.76). On the other hand, analysis of mean score of head teachers indicates that in observation of head teachers (mean 2.56), this code is not followed by teachers in practice.

ANOVA analysis ($f=31.96$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.163 , $p=0.035$), teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.274 , $p=0.012$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (-0.859 , $p=0.000$) and teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (-0.970 , $p=0.000$).

Above results show a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices, it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices.

Table 7
Teacher teaches Nazara prescribed part of Holy Quran

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results			LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO	
TP	4.19								
TPR	4.12	61.68	0.000	0.470*	0.652*	0.581*	1.144*	1.100*	
HTO	3.02			(0.002)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	
STO	3.54								

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 7 is about "Teacher teaches Nazara prescribed part of Holy Quran". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 4.19. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 4.12 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 3.02 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 3.54. These values indicate that teachers have strong thinking about teaching of Nazara prescribed part of Holy Quran (mean 4.19). The analysis of mean score of head teachers and students regarding their observation about the application of this code by teachers indicates that in observation of head teachers (mean 3.02) and in observation of students (3.54), this code is poorly followed by teachers in practice.

The ANOVA analysis ($f=61.68$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a strong significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and teachers' practices (0.470 , $p=0.002$), and teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.652 , $p=0.000$). The significant mean difference between teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.581 , $p=0.000$). The significant difference between teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (1.144 , $p=0.000$) and difference between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (1.100 , $p=0.000$).

The ANOVA results explore a strong gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices, it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices and also admit this.

Table 8

Teacher teaches prescribed part of Holy Quran that students learn by heart

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	3.92							
TPR	3.90	43.76	0.000	-0.137 (0.152)	0.552* (0.000)	0.967* (0.000)	1.004* (0.000)	0.589* (0.000)
HTO	3.37							
STO	2.95							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 8 is about "Teacher teaches prescribed part of Holy Quran that students learn by heart". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 3.92. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.90 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 3.37 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 2.95. These values indicate that teachers have positive agreement about the statement (mean 3.92). They admit that they follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.90). On the other hand, analysis of mean score of head teachers (mean 2.60) and observation of students (2.20) showed this code is not followed by teachers in practice.

ANOVA analysis ($f=43.76$, $p=0.000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.552, $p=0.000$), teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.967, $p=0.000$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (1.004, $p=0.000$) and teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (-0.589, $p=0.000$).

Here a gap is discovered between teachers' perceptions and their practices; it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices.

Table 9

Teacher teaches Urdu translation of prescribed Suras and Ahadees

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	3.89							
TPR	3.80	15.54	0.000	0.243 (0.054)	0.519 (0.000)	0.241* (0.053)	0.537* (0.000)	0.459* (0.000)
HTO	3.35							
STO	3.37							

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 9 is about "Teacher teaches Urdu translation of prescribed Suras and Ahadees". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 3.89. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.80 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 3.35 whereas mean score value of students' observations is 3.37. It indicates that teachers have positive thinking about the statement (mean 3.89). They also admit that they follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.80). While, analysis of mean score head teachers (mean 3.35) and observation of students (3.37), points out that this code is poorly followed by teachers in practice.

The ANOVA analysis ($f=15.54$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.519, $p=0.000$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (0.537, $p=0.000$) and between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation (0.459, $p=0.000$).

The LSD analysis discovers a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices; it indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices.

Table 10

Teacher teaches Arkaan e Islam as given in text book

Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
		F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR& STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
TP	3.98							
TPR	3.78	71.51	0.000	0.200 (0.055)	0.859 (0.000)	0.759* (0.000)	1.319* (0.000)	1.119* (0.000)
HTO	2.66							

STO 3.02

Note: TP= Teacher perception, TPR= Teacher claim about his own practice, STO= Students' observation about teacher, HTO= Head teacher's observation *Score in () is the mean difference

Table 10 is about "Teacher teaches Arkaan e Islam as given in text book". Mean score of teachers' perceptions (TP) is 3.98. Mean score of teachers' claim about their practices is 3.78 and mean score of head teachers' observations is 2.66 while mean score value of students' observations is 3.02. These values indicate that teachers have positive agreement about teaching of Arkaan-E-Islam as given in text book (mean 3.98). The teachers think that teaching of Arkaan-E-Islam as given in text book can be helpful to improve students' learning. They also admit that they try to follow this code in their practices (mean score 3.78). The analysis of mean score of head teachers (mean 2.66), discloses that this code is not followed by teachers in practice.

The ANOVA analysis ($f=71.51$, $p=0.0000$) indicates a significant mean difference between groups at 0.05 level of significance. LSD analysis also indicates significant mean difference between teachers' perceptions and students' observations (0.859, $p=0.000$), teachers' claim about their practice and their students' observation (0.759, $p=0.000$), teachers' perceptions and head teachers' observation (1.319, $p=0.000$) and between teachers' practices and head teachers' observation is (1.119, $p=0.000$).

This reveals a gap between teachers' perceptions and their practices. It indicates that teachers do not follow this code in their practices.

Table 11

Summary table of the analysis

Factors	Variables	Mean score	ANOVA Results		LSD Results				
			F value	Sig.	Difference Between TP&TPR	Difference Between TP&STO	Difference Between TPR&STO	Difference Between TP&HTO	Difference Between TPR&HTO
Character building and social training	TP	3.67	87.54	0.000	5.238*	1.276*	4.787*	4.390*	-0.885*
	TPR	3.35							
	HTO	2.93							
	STO	2.59							
Teaching of Islamic studies	TP	3.91	60.39	0.000	3.267*	2.785*	-0.481	2.730*	-.537*
	TPR	3.09							
	HTO	3.01							
	STO	2.96							

Note: Item Nos. 1 to 5 that analyzed in table Nos. 1 to 5 belong to factor character building and social training whereas item Nos. 6 to 10 that analyzed in table Nos. 6 to 10 named as factor teaching of Islamic studies

Table 11 reveals that teachers have positive opinions about the both two factors that are character building and social training and teaching of Islamic studies in case of teachers' practices again positive claim was shown by the teachers. Head teachers observations did not cross checked the teachers claim about their practices regarding teaching of Islamic studies but about both factors students' observation did not verified teachers' practices. Hence gap between perceptions and practices about two factors is visible in LSD analysis.

Whereas the ANOVA evaluation in term of F- Score and p-score regarding the two factors shows strong significant mean difference between groups. Thus the analysis discovers a strong difference between what they think and what they act.

Conclusion and Discussion

The aim of this study was to study the role of teachers in teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. The study was focus to explore teachers' perceptions and practices and investigate the gaps between their thinking and performance in perspective of teachers' code of conduct. The results of Analysis of the data showed that teachers have clear thought and awareness about the teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information as prescribed in teachers' code of conduct. It was revealed that teachers strongly acknowledged that they should act upon the instructions developed for them about the two factors character building and social training and teaching of Islamic studies. On other hand analyzed results concluded that teachers' practices about the two factors were not matched or verified their claims. That explores a distinct gap between teachers' perceptions and their claim about the practices. So it was found that teachers are not acting upon the instructions narrated in teachers' code of conduct in their practices. That is a matter of serious concern

for the teaching outputs, teaching profession and educational managers to bring a positive change in the situation.

The results of the study showed that it was a good attempt as it brought out a good understanding and awareness of teachers about the code of conduct concerning to teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. The results of the study can be fruitful in providing effective training of teacher educators during induction period and also in-service teacher training. The study is also a helpful tool for the educational planners and monitoring authorities while issuance instructions and its implementation in the school education department.

The results of this study may be used in strengthening the instructional planning mechanism and it can be source of reducing frustration of stakeholders about school education in Pakistan. The outcomes the study indicate hassle in obeying the instructions of the higher authorities by the school teachers. It is also revealed that professionals and teachers of the teaching profession disregarding the rules and did not obey guidelines of the higher authorities.

The results of this study are also inclining or vary with the conclusions of the pervious such studies conducted on the topic. Hashim (2005) conducted a study on the topic "Rethinking Islamic Education in Facing the Challenges of the Twenty-first Century" reflected three challenges that are factors of incapability of Islamic Education the first is teaching techniques second is the curriculum and the third is students' attitude toward facing modern challenges. Teaching techniques or pedagogy are basic tool in hands of the teacher through they perform task of transfer of knowledge and train the new generation. Teachers' code of conduct provides guidelines about performing their job effectively. The family, school and community are three main stockholders in providing education to the younger generation (Epstein, 2018). The study concluded along with family and community school is a basic and vital component in educating the younger generation. Thus teachers' role in transferring education is ever important. Al-Qarni (2008) affirms that absence of commitment to ethics and Islamic moral values in teaching has a damaging effect on the educational and learning process. Islamic teachings and scholars mainly focus moral teaching and training of the students. As a complete code of conduct Islam aims to train its followers morally that can producesocially balanced life.

Al-Ghamdi (2006) concluded that the teachers' good characters put positive impact on the moral of the students and the society. Teachers' effective role in providing basic Islamic education important for students moral training and becoming responsible citizens. Conroy and Emerson (2004) stated that religion confidently effects upon ethical attitudes similarly religiosity determinates ethical values. The religion especially Islam mainly focuses on social training that based on specific ethical and moral values. Teachers can do a lot in this sense by teaching Islamic education effectively.

The results of the study showed the strong gap between teachers' perceptions and practices regarding the two factors. The reasons for existence of these gaps may be improper training, poor monitoring by school heads and other management bodies, the lack of teachers' interest, absence of implementation mechanism and lack of professionalism in teaching profession or may be this because of teacher's overburden tasks to complete courses timely and just to focusing on factor of producing students' academic upgradation and academic excellence in the form of high grades in examinations. Thus, it is recommended that school education department should focus on teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information and appoint firmly trained and motivated teachers in ethical training of students. This can be done by developing a mechanism for teachers' practice about teaching of Islamic studies and basic Islamic information. Moreover, a study at large scale on reasons behind the situation may be conducted in Pakistan and other parts of the world. Further study should also compare the attitude of teachers regarding professional code of ethics on the bases of gender, qualification, age and other demographic variables.

This study did not involve analysis based on different demographic factors related to teachers. SO, in future studies may be conducted in Pakistan and other countries focusing on different demographic variables like gender, qualification, and age. Similarly, futuristic studies may be conducted in other educational institutions like universities, colleges and higher secondary schools.

This study was limited to public sector secondary school teachers whereas the private sector secondary school teachers were not part of the study. Area of sample of the study was narrowed to four districts of Punjab province of Pakistan only. Future study may be conducted about the private sector secondary school teachers in comparison of public sector secondary school teachers focusing the same area of population. According to the researchers' own perception gaps between teachers' practices regarding teachers code of conduct in perspective of teaching of Islamic studies are due to improper training and poor strategies of implementation. Thus concerning authorities are requested that they should tackle this shortage with effective measures.

References

- Abdur Razzaq, H. (2012). Islamic ethics and intrinsic value of human being. *Journal of Philosophical Investigation*, 6, 11.

- Adnan, A.R. (2002). Tarbiyah rabbaniyyah (divine education) and its significance in the development of husnu'l-khuluq. *Muslim Education Quarterly*, 19, 16-29.
- Al-A'ali, M. (2008). Computer ethics for the computer professional from an Islamic point of view. *Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society*, 6, 28-45.
- Al-Ghamdi, H. (2006). *Professional ethics among Muslim teachers and its impact on the moral education of the individual and society*. Research presented to the 13th annual conference, held in the Saudi Society of Educational and Psychological Sciences (Justin), Faculty of Education, King Saud University, Riyadh.
- Al-Mafdi, S. (2004). *Preparation of the teacher of Islamic education in light of the immediate and future needs of high school students*. A research presented to the 16th scientific conference of the Egyptian Society for Curriculum and Teaching Methods, entitled (teacher formation "preparation and training"). Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/3yH89m>.
- Al-Qarni, A. A. G. (2008). *Work values contained in the Teaching code of Ethics from the Islamic Perspective and the Mechanism for activating it among teachers* (Unpublished thesis). Umm Al Qura University, Saudi Arabia.
- Al-Rawahy, K. H. (2013). Engineering Education and Sustainable Development: The Missing Link. *Procedia-Soc. Behav. Sci.*, 102, 392-401.
- Al-Sharaf, A. (2013). *Developing scientific thinking methods and applications in Islamic education*. *Education*, 133(3), 201-215.
- An-Nahlawi, A. (2010). *Isool Altarbia Alaslamiyah Wa Asalibaha* [Assets of Islamic education and its Methods], 28, 29&90, Damascus, Syria.
- Arifin Bin, M. (2004). *Quranic pedagogy and its practices in the teaching of the Arabic language*. (Doctoral dissertation). Available from The International Islamic University Malaysia Matriculation Centre.
- Asyafah, A. (2014). The Method of Tadabur Qur'an: What Are the Student Views? *International Education Studies*, 7(6).
- Capli, F. A. (2015). *The role of school principals in promoting teaching ethics among teachers from principals and teachers perspective in Makkah public schools* (Unpublished thesis). Umm Al Qura University, Saudi Arabia.
- Conroy, S., & Emerson, T. (2004). Business ethics and religion: Religiosity as a predictor of ethical awareness among students. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 50, 383-396
- Deshach, N. (2014). The Profession of Education, Ethics and the Role of Teacher. *Journal of Research and Humanities*, 8, 218-237.
- Epstein, J. L. (2018). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. London: Routledge Publications.
- Ghani, K.A., Khadijah, A.R., & Embi, M.A. (2003). *Research Report on the Level of Professionalism of Islamic Education and Arabic Language Teachers: A Study of Religious Secondary Schools in Kelantan*. Faculty of Education, National University of Malaysia.
- Hamad, S. (2004). *Assalib Tadrees Altrbah Alislamiyah Alshaaiah Altee Uastakhdmha Moalmy Altrbaih Alaslamiyah Fi Almarhalah Alasahsia Alilaafi Gaza Wa Mbarrat Istkhdamaha* volume 12- second Issue, P.503-52
- Hashim, R. (2005). Rethinking Islamic Education in Facing the Challenges of the Twenty-first Century. *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, 22(4), 133-147.
- Mohd, S. A. R. (2013). Educator's Adab inventory: infusing Islamic manner and Islamic work ethics in teaching profession. *WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings*.
- Nadia, M. (2015). Professional ethics of teachers in educational institutions nanigopal malo. *International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS)*, 1(6), 94-98.
- Sadia, A. (2015). *Norwegian religion and culture influence identity and ethics of young generation of Muslims*. School of Mission and Theology.
- Thomas, B. (2003). The moral dimensions of teacher student interactions in Malaysian secondary schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educators and Education*, 18, 190-201.
- Van Driel, J.H., & Berry, A. 2012. Teacher Professional Development Focusing on Pedagogical Content Knowledge. *Educational Researcher*, 41(1), 26-28.
- Yunanda, R. A., & Abd. Majid, N. (2011). The contribution of Islamic ethics towards ethical accounting practices. *Issues in Social and Environmental Accounting*, 5(1/2), 124-137.

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